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Effects of Livestock Urine Rate and Methods of Application on the Proximate Composition of Pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis*) in South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This experiment was conducted on the research farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Nigeria. In Nigeria, where first-class protein such as fish and meat are very expensive and out of the reach of the poor, and where the major sources of nutrients are purely starchy foods, pumpkin, which is a leafy source of protein, becomes an alternative for the poor. The need, therefore, to determine the proximate composition of pumpkin grown under livestock urine necessitated this study. The experimental design was a $3 \times 3 \times 4$ split-plot factorial replicated three times. There were three main factors. Factor A is the source of urine, Factor B is the rate of application, and Factor C is the method of application. The sources of urine were goat, rabbit, and cow urine; methods were ring, double placement, and spot, while the rates were 0, 200, 300, and 400 L/ha. The results revealed that the highest protein, crude fiber, and ash were recorded in pumpkins grown under goat urine at a 300 L/ha rate of application using the ring method. It is, therefore, recommended that, to boost nutrient intake in the studied area, goat urine at 300 L/ha using the ring method of application should be employed by pumpkin farmers.

Keywords: livestock urine, proximate methods of application, rate of application

INTRODUCTION

Fluted pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis* Hook. f.), called Ugu in the eastern part of Nigeria, belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae (Ndukwe et al., 2025). Pumpkin is usually cultivated for its leaves, shoots, and seeds, which are harvested when the need arises (Tijani-Eniola, 2002). Pumpkin has industrial benefits in that oil from the seeds is used for the production of soaps (Esiaba, 1982). Flour from the seeds is also used for the preparation of bread and protein-rich snacks (Ganni, 2003). Pumpkin also has nutritional value in that it contains vitamins such as vitamins A, B, C, B2, and B3, minerals, and crude protein (Odiaka et al., 2001). In addition, pumpkin possesses medicinal value because the seeds and leaves contain anti-diabetic properties, which help to regulate and reduce sugar levels in diabetic patients (Iyagba et al., 2013). The seeds contain oleic acid, which helps to improve sperm count in males (Okokon et al., 2009). Pumpkin also contains antioxidants, which are used as blood tonics in women who have just given birth (Alada, 2000). More so, oil from the seed contains lactating

properties; thus, it is highly used by nursing mothers to improve milk production (Akag et al., 2010). Studies have also shown that pumpkin seeds possess anti-cancer properties and are therefore used to prevent prostate cancer (Akoroda, 1998). Pumpkin protects the heart and helps prevent cardiovascular diseases (Oboh et al., 2006). Pumpkin is a very useful vegetable for humans because it contains protein, crude fiber, fat, carbohydrates, and minerals (Ndor et al., 2013). Organic manure is non-chemical origin materials added to the soil to improve yield. They are not expensive, easy to access, and do not affect the ecosystem adversely, while increasing the soil microbiota needed for organic manure decomposition. Organic manure could be either in liquid or solid form (Izaicrralde et al., 2000; and Abustam et al., 2018). The agronomic characteristics of *Telfairia occidentalis* growing under organic manure are better than those grown under inorganic fertilizer (Okporie et al., 2012). The best leaves produced by organic manure treatment could be attributed to the carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C:N). Adein et al. (2011) reported that organic manure improves the rate of nutrient absorption in *Telfairia occidentalis*.

Rabbit urine has been revealed to contain NPK, which are essential for proper plant growth (Said et al., 2018). Carbon organic content on essential elements in organic manure is proven to be present in rabbit urine (Stark, 2008). Rabbit urine is a good substitute for chemical fertilizer since it has minimal risk to the ecosystem and still provides nutrients for the development and growth of the plant (Indabo and Abubaker, 2019). Goat urine is also very cheap to get, rich in nitrogen, and improves the soil texture, thus creating a better growing environment for the crops, which in turn increases plant yield. Cow urine has been known to be useful as a bio fertilizer and bio pesticide in agricultural operations, as it destroys a lot of pesticide and herbicide-resistant bacteria, viruses, and fungi. Cow urine has so many biological activities, like antioxidant, anti-diabetic, antitumor, and anti-protozoa (Krishnamurh et al.; 2013).

Livestock urine is easy to get, eco-friendly, improves the soil texture and structure, and releases organic matter that improves the soil's porosity and water-retaining capacity.

In Nigeria, where first-class protein sources such as meat and fish are very expensive and out of the reach of the poor, and where their major source of nutrients or starchy foods, pumpkin, which is a leafy source of protein, crude fibre, ash, and fat, becomes a better alternative for the poor populace (Fai et al., 2013).

The proximate composition of a crop refers to the nutritional content of that particular crop for man. According to Fai et al. (2013), they reported that pumpkin leaves contain 3.5% moisture, 11% ash, 2.5% crude fiber, 6.9% fat, 6.5% protein, and 74.0% carbohydrate.

Yahaya et al. (2023) reported that *T. occidentalis* contains 49.44 ± 0.55 carbohydrates, 14.66 ± 1.04 crude fiber, 71.40 ± 0.31 moisture content, 22.45 ± 0.5 protein, 4.80 ± 0.34 crude fat, and 8.60 ± 0.21 ash.

Onuguh et al. (2022) stated that the proximate composition of *T. occidentalis* ranges as follows: 91.25 ± 0.38 to $92.45 \pm 1.02\%$ moisture content, 2.98 ± 0.22 to $3.51 \pm 0.13\%$ crude fiber, 2.65 ± 0.05 to $3.29 \pm 0.15\%$ carbohydrates, 1.05 ± 0.03 to $2.06 \pm 0.15\%$ protein, 0.25 ± 0.05 to $0.45 \pm 0.04\%$ fat, and 0.118 ± 0.02 to $0.28 \pm 0.04\%$ ash.

Thus, the need to determine the effect of livestock urine on the nutrient content of pumpkin necessitated this study.

Therefore, the main objective of this study was to determine the effect of livestock urine on the proximate composition of pumpkin leaves.

Specific Objective

- To compare the efficiency of different sources of livestock urine on the proximate composition of *T. occidentalis* leaves.
- To determine the rate of livestock urine that gives the highest nutrient (Protein, Crude Fibre, ash & fat)
- To determine the method of application that gives the highest nutrient (Protein, Crude Fibre, ash & fat)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental Site

This research took place at the research farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Southern Delta University, Ozoro. Ozoro is in Isoko North Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. It has a mean annual rainfall of 2,000 mm to 3,000 mm and a mean annual temperature of about 28 to 30°C.

2.2 Sources of Planting Materials and Livestock Urine

Pumpkin pods were purchased from local pumpkin farmers in the study area. Cow urine was collected from the school cattle rearer, while rabbit and goat urine were collected from rabbit and goat farmers, respectively.

2.3 Experimental Design

The design for the experiment was a split ($3 \times 3 \times 4$) factorial experiment replicated three times.

There were three (3) main factors, which were:

- a) Source of urine
- b) Rate of application
- c) Method of application

The levels consisted of the following:

- i. **Sources of urine:** Cow, goat, and rabbit urine.
- ii. **Methods of application:** Ring, double placement, and spot methods.
- iii. **Rates of application:** 0 L/ha, 200 L/ha, 300 L/ha, and 400 L/ha.

2.4 Planting

Pumpkin seeds were planted directly into the field at a plant spacing of 50 cm \times 60 cm. Each treatment had ninety-six stands, which were replicated three times, giving a grand total of two hundred and eighty-eight stands. Therefore, 4×3 blocks replicated three times equaled $288 \times 3 = 864$ stands of pumpkin. At germination, three stands were tagged for data collection.

2.5 Treatment Application

The urine collected was allowed to ferment for a period of two weeks (14 days) before application. The treatments applied were goat, rabbit, and cow urine using different methods of application (ring, double placement, and spot methods) at different rates of application (0 L/ha, 200 L/ha, 300 L/ha, and 400 L/ha). For 200 L/ha, each stand received 6 cl; 300 L/ha received 9 cl, while 400 L/ha received 12 cl.

2.6 Harvesting and Proximate Analysis

Sixteen weeks after planting, harvesting was done. The harvested leaves were carefully placed in clean labeled polythene bags for packaging and identification of each treatment. They were sent to the laboratory for proximate analysis. Analysis was carried out using standard methods (AOAC) for determining ash (furnace), crude protein (Kjeldahl), fat (solvent extraction), and crude fibre gravimetric analysis (weighing the residue for crude fibre). Carbohydrate was determined using spectrophotometric techniques (colour change).

RESULTS

3.1 Chemical properties of the soils of the study area

The chemical properties of the soils of the study area are presented in Table 4.1. The results show that the pH value of the soil was 4.33 (1:2 H₂O). Organic carbon was 0.47%, while organic matter was 1.32%. Nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium were measured in mg/kg units. The nitrogen value was 0.10 mg/kg, the phosphorus value was 4.67 mg/kg, and the potassium (K) value was 0.41 mg/kg. The elements sodium (Na), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and iron (Fe) had the following values: 0.40 cmol kg⁻¹, 2.10 cmol kg⁻¹, 1.00 cmol kg⁻¹, and 0.19 cmol kg⁻¹, respectively. Lead (Pb) value was 0.03 ppm, zinc (Zn) value was 0.24 ppm, while copper (Cu) value was 0.24 ppm.

Table 3.1: Chemical properties of the soil of the study area

Chemical Property	Value
pH 1:2 (H ₂ O)	4.33
OC (%)	0.77
OM (%)	1.32
N (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.10
P (mg kg ⁻¹)	4.67
K (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.41
Na (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.40
Ca (cmol kg ⁻¹)	2.10
Mg (cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.00
Fe (ppm)	0.19
Zn (ppm)	0.24
Cu (ppm)	0.24
Pb (ppm)	0.03

3.2 Livestock urine composition

Table 4.2 reveals the results of the analysis of the three sources of livestock urine (goat, cow, and rabbit). The results show that the values of nitrogen (N) ranged between 0.33–0.55%. The highest (0.55%) was recorded for goat, while 0.37% and 0.33% were recorded for cow and rabbit, respectively. The value of phosphorus ranged between 6.32–8.84 mg/100 g. The highest (8.84 mg/100 g) was recorded for goat, against 7.53 and 6.32 for cow and rabbit, respectively. For potassium (K), it ranged between 6.14–14.04 mg/100 g. The highest (14.04 mg/100 g) was recorded for goat urine, compared to 11.31 and 6.94 for cow and rabbit, respectively. The value of calcium (Ca) also ranged between 2.68–9.46 mg/100 g. The highest (7.46 mg/100 g) was recorded for goat urine, compared with 5.56 and 2.68 for cow and rabbit, respectively. Magnesium (Mg) followed the same trend, with goat urine having the highest (2.14 mg/100 g), compared to cow and rabbit, which had 1.62 and 1.42 mg/100 g, respectively. For iron, which ranged between 0.10–0.20 ppm, the highest (0.20 ppm) was recorded for goat, against 0.16 and 0.10 for cow and rabbit, respectively. For manganese (Mn), all treatments had the same value of 0.10 ppm, while lead (Pb) for cow and rabbit had the same value of 0.01 ppm, with goat having 0.02 ppm. For zinc (Zn), goat and rabbit had the same value of 0.25 ppm, while cow had 0.23 ppm. For copper (Cu), the value ranged between 0.07–0.20 ppm. The highest (0.20 ppm) was recorded for the cow, against 0.17 and 0.07 recorded for the goat and rabbit, respectively.

Table 3.2: Results of the analysis of the three sources of livestock urine (goat, cow, and rabbit)

Source	N (%)	P (mg/100g)	K (mg/100g)	Ca (mg/100g)	Mg (mg/100g)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Pb (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Cu (ppm)
Goat	0.55	8.84	14.04	7.46	2.14	0.20	0.10	0.02	0.25	0.17
Cow	0.37	7.53	11.31	5.56	1.62	0.16	0.10	0.01	0.23	0.20
Rabbit	0.33	6.32	6.14	2.68	1.42	0.10				

3.3 Effects of Three Sources of Livestock Urine on Proximate Composition of *T. occidentalis*

Table 3.3 revealed the effects of three sources of livestock urine on the proximate composition of *T. occidentalis* leaves.

The moisture results ranged between 75.67 and 75.81. The highest moisture content (75.81) was recorded in *T. occidentalis* dressed with rabbit urine, while the lowest (75.67) was recorded in pumpkin grown under cow urine.

For ash, the results ranged between 2.04 and 2.29. The highest ash content (2.29) was recorded in pumpkin grown under goat urine treatment, while the lowest (2.04) ash content was recorded in

pumpkin grown under rabbit urine treatment. There was a significant difference among the treatments at a 5% level of probability.

For fat, the results ranged between 3.41 and 3.54. The highest fat content (3.54) was recorded in pumpkin grown under cow urine, while the lowest (3.41) fat content was recorded in rabbit urine treatment. There was a significant difference among the treatments.

For crude fiber, the results ranged between 7.32 and 7.49. The highest crude fiber (7.49) was observed in pumpkin grown using goat urine, while the least (7.32) crude fiber was obtained in pumpkin grown using rabbit urine. There was a significant difference among the treatments.

For protein, the results ranged between 9.44 and 9.70. The highest protein (9.70) was obtained in pumpkin grown under goat urine, while the least (9.44) protein was recorded in pumpkin grown under rabbit urine.

For carbohydrates, the results ranged between 1.59 and 1.74. The highest carbohydrate content (1.74) was obtained in pumpkin grown using rabbit urine, while the least (1.59) carbohydrate content was recorded in pumpkin grown under rabbit urine. There was a significant difference between rabbit urine and other treatments at a 5% level of probability.

Table 3.3: Effects of Three Sources of Livestock Urine Application on the Proximate Composition of *T. occidentalis* leaves

Urine	Moisture	Ash	Fat	Crude oil	Protein	Carbohydrate
Cow	75.67a	2.14b	3.54a	7.41b	9.56b	1.60b
Goat	75.79a	2.29a	3.47b	7.49b	9.70a	1.59b
Rabbit	75.81a	2.04c	3.4c	7.32c	9.44c	1.74a

The results in Table 3.4 showed that pumpkin crop grown using rabbit urine at 300 L/ha had the highest moisture content (76.23). There was a significant difference among the treatments at a 5% level of probability, while the least moisture content (75.38) was recorded in the control treatment.

For ash, pumpkin grown under goat urine at the rate of 300 L/ha had the highest (2.46) ash component. However, there was no significant difference among the treatments.

For crude fiber, the results revealed that pumpkin grown at 300 L/ha rate of application had the highest (7.60) crude fiber, while the least (7.22) was recorded in the control treatment. However, there was no significant difference among the treatments at a 5% level of probability.

For protein, pumpkin grown under urine treatment using 300 L/ha rate of application had the highest (10.08) protein content. There was a significant difference among the treatments, while the least (9.31) was recorded in the control treatment.

For fat, the results showed that pumpkin grown under cow urine at 400 L/ha rate of application had the highest (3.69) fat content. There was a significant difference among the treatments, while the least (3.18) fat content was recorded in the control treatment.

For carbohydrates, the results revealed that pumpkin grown under cow urine using 200 L/ha rate of application had the highest (2.07) carbohydrate content. There was a significant difference among the treatments at a 5% level of probability, while the least (1.29) carbohydrate content was recorded in the control treatment.

Table 3.4: effect of livestock urine & rate of application on proximate composition of T.O leaves

Livestock Urine	Rate of Application	Moisture content	Ash	Crude fibre	Protein	Fat	Carbohydrate
Cow	0	75.38f	1.60d	7.22c	9.31f	3.18d	1.29cd
	200	75.81cd	2.50a	7.57a	9.58bc	3.53b	1.29cd
	300	75.62c	1.99c	7.41b	9.67b	3.67a	2.07a
	400	75.86c	2.45a	7.55a	9.51cb	3.69a	1.98ab
Goat	0	75.38f	1.60d	7.22c	9.31f	3.18d	1.29cd
	200	75.71dc	2.09c	7.57a	9.60bc	3.47bc	1.83ab
	300	75.94cd	2.46c	7.60a	10.08a	3.55b	1.92ab
	400	76.09b	2.04c	7.59a	9.58bc	3.68a	1.33c
Rabbit	0	75.38f	1.60d	7.22c	9.31f	3.18d	1.29cd
	200	15.69c	2.45a	7.57a	9.36cf	3.47bc	2.04a
	300	76.23a	2.20b	7.38b	9.58bc	3.66a	1.80b
	400	75.70de	2.45a	7.25c	9.49cd	3.40c	1.79b

3.5 Effects of Livestock Urine and Method of Application on Proximate Composition of *T. occidentalis* Leaves

Table 3.3 revealed that *T. occidentalis* grown under rabbit urine using the ring method of application had the highest (76.29) moisture content.

There was a significant difference among the treatments for ash. The results also show that pumpkin grown under goat urine using the ring method of application had the highest (2.48%) ash content, while the lowest (1.82%) ash content was recorded in cow urine using the spot method of application.

For fat, the results presented show that pumpkin grown under goat urine using the ring method of application recorded the highest (3.63%) fat content, while the lowest (3.30%) fat content was recorded in goat urine using the spot method of application.

For crude fiber, the results show that pumpkin grown under goat urine using the ring method of application recorded the highest (7.52%) crude fiber. There was a significant difference among the treatments. The least (7.30%) crude fiber was recorded in pumpkin grown under rabbit urine using the spot method of application.

For protein, the presented table reveals that pumpkin grown under goat urine using the ring method of application had the highest (9.80%) protein content, while the least (9.32%) protein was recorded in rabbit urine using the spot method of application.

For carbohydrates, the results show that pumpkin grown under rabbit urine had the highest (2.23%). There was a significant difference among the treatments at the 5% level of probability, while the least (0.77%) carbohydrates was recorded in pumpkin grown under goat urine using the spot method of application.

3.5 Effects of Livestock Urine and Method of Application on Proximate Composition of *T. occidentalis* Leaves

Livestock Urine	Application Method	Moisture Content	Ash	Fat	Crude fiber	Protein	Carbohydrate
Cow	Double placement	75.38f	2.21cd	3.60a	7.43bc	9.56cd	1.73bc
	Ring	75.86c	2.39b	3.63ab	7.46b	9.64bc	2.13a
	Spot	75.77c	1.82f	3.40de	7.34de	9.47d	1.78b
Goat	Double placement	75.60d	2.11e	3.54bc	7.47b	9.66b	1.40e
	Ring	76.08b	2.48a	3.58ab	7.58a	9.80a	1.68bc
	Spot	75.49ef	1.87f	3.30f	7.41bcd	9.64b	0.77f
Rabbit	Double placement	75.77c	2.21c	3.47cd	7.31e	9.48d	1.56cd
	Ring	76.29a	2.13de	3.40de	7.36cd	9.55d	2.23a
	Spot	75.57de	2.16de	3.36ef	7.03e	9.32e	1.53de

DISCUSSION

The outcome of the experiment proved that livestock urine, rate and methods of application had great influence on the proximate composition of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves throughout the experimental period. The results revealed that *Telfairia occidentalis* grown under goat urine at 300 L/ha using the ring method had the highest (10.08) protein, (7.60) crude fibre, and 2.46% ash. There were significant differences among the treatments at the 5% level of probability. This finding does not agree with Fai et al. (2013) and Onuguh et al. (2022), who reported lower percentages of proximate composition of *Telfairia occidentalis*. They reported 6.5% protein, $3.51 \pm 0.13\%$ ash, and 2.5% crude fiber. This was not in line with the findings of (Salahu, 2005), who stated that pumpkin contained 6.5% protein. The finding does not agree with (Gafer et al., 2009) who reported that pumpkin leaves contained 2.6% crude fiber. The variation in results could be attributed to the various types of urine, weight, and method of application used. Climate, the nature of soil, and location could be a great source of variation in findings.

The result showed that pumpkin leaves had a high percentage of protein that replaced worn-out tissues in adults and was necessary for proper growth and development in children (Samson and Isaac, 2019).

The result also captures a higher percentage of crude fibre, which helps to reduce cholesterol levels, diabetes, and decrease the risk of cardiovascular disease (Oboh et al., 2006).

For rate of application, the findings agreed with (Oroka, 2015), who reported that pumpkins that received the highest application of liquid organic manure at the rate of 360 L/ha had the highest leaf area and leaf area index.

The size of the leaf area and the leaf area index influences the amount of nutrients present in a leaf. This finding also contradicts (Akanbi et al., 2000; Usman, 2015), who reported that an increase in the number of leaves and leaf area is attributed to the application of a high rate of liquid organic manure. The greater the leaf area, the better the photosynthesis, which in turn influences the nutritive capacity of the plant. For the method of application, the results agreed with Obi et al. (2005), who reported that the ring method of application shows significant differences in leaf area and leaf area index, which are functions of the quality of nutrient availability in the leaf. This finding also agreed with Olufolaji et al. (2002), who reported that an increase in leaf area and fruit production in *Celosia argentea* dressed with the ring method of application.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings revealed that *Telfairia occidentalis* grown under goat urine at 300 L/ha using the ring method of application had the highest percentage of protein, crude fibre, and ash and a lower percentage of carbohydrates.

It is therefore recommended that *Telfairia occidentalis* farmers should adopt the usage of goat urine at 300 L/ha using method of application since it helps to improve the nutrient status of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves which invariably boost the nutrient intake of the final consumer.

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